

Short Linear Motif Architecture of ORF4 Suggests Lineage-Specific Host Interaction Strategies in Anelloviruses

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Abstract

Open reading frame 4 (ORF4) of anelloviruses is poorly characterized despite evidence suggesting a role in host-virus interactions.¹ To explore potential functional architecture, ORF4 proteins from representative torque teno virus (TTV) and torque teno midi virus (TTMDV) isolates were analyzed for short linear motifs (SLiMs) using the Eukaryotic Linear Motif (ELM) resource. Comparative motif mapping identified recurrent host-interaction motifs embedded within largely intrinsically disordered regions of the proteins. Several motif classes, including PP1 phosphatase docking motifs, proline-rich SH3-binding ligands, and canonical 14-3-3 interaction motifs, were detected across multiple isolates. Density-normalized comparisons with composition-preserving shuffled controls indicated that PP1 docking motifs and SH3 ligands occur at elevated densities in TTV sequences and display non-random positional organization along the protein sequence, with PP1 motifs preferentially localized toward C-terminal regions and SH3 ligands concentrated in N-terminal and central segments. In contrast, TTMDV sequences exhibited distinct motif compositions with fewer proline-rich interaction motifs. Together, these findings support a model in which ORF4 functions as a flexible, intrinsically disordered interaction scaffold capable of recruiting host regulatory proteins through distributed motif-mediated interfaces. The observed lineage-specific differences in motif architecture further suggest diversification of host interaction strategies within the *Anelloviridae*.

Keywords: Torque teno virus; torquevirus; torque teno midi virus; gammatorquevirus; *Anelloviridae*; short linear motifs; ORF4 protein; virology; computational biology.

Introduction

Anelloviruses are small, non-enveloped viruses with circular single-stranded DNA genomes that are highly prevalent in human populations and establish persistent, asymptomatic infections.¹ Members of the family *Anelloviridae*, including torque teno viruses (TTV) and torque teno midi viruses (TTMDV), exhibit extensive genetic diversity while maintaining a broadly conserved genomic organization.² Despite their ubiquity and long-term persistence in the host, the molecular mechanisms underlying anellovirus replication and host interaction remain poorly characterized. In particular, some viral open reading frames encode proteins for which no definitive biochemical function has been experimentally established.³

Among these, ORF4 represents one of the least characterized proteins encoded by torqueviruses. ORF4 proteins are relatively small and lack recognizable catalytic domains or well-defined structural folds based on conventional homology searches.⁴ Such features suggest that ORF4 may function primarily through protein-protein interaction networks rather than through intrinsic enzymatic activity.⁵ Many viral regulatory proteins operate through intrinsically disordered regions that contain SLiMs, which mediate transient interactions with host regulatory factors. These motifs are typically short, degenerate sequence elements that enable viruses to recruit host signalling machinery, modulate phosphorylation networks, or scaffold multiprotein complexes.^{6,7,8}

Computational prediction of SLiMs provides a useful framework for identifying potential interaction interfaces in proteins lacking canonical domains; however, motif prediction is inherently prone to false positives due to the aforementioned short and degenerate nature of motif consensus sequences. Consequently, rigorous interpretation of SLiM predictions requires appropriate background controls to distinguish functional motif enrichment from occurrences expected purely from amino acid composition.⁹ One common strategy is the use of shuffled-sequence null models that preserve underlying residue or dipeptide composition while disrupting potential biological patterning.^{10,11}

In this study, ORF4 proteins from representative TTV and TTMDV isolates were analyzed to investigate their potential regulatory architecture. Short linear motif predictions were generated using the ELM resource and evaluated against dipeptide-preserving shuffled controls to identify motifs that exceed compositional expectations. In addition, positional distribution of motifs, intrinsic disorder predictions, and comparative analysis across viral lineages were used to assess whether predicted interaction elements form coherent structural patterns rather than random background matches.

This approach enables the identification of candidate regulatory motifs and provides insight into the potential interaction strategies employed by ORF4. By integrating motif enrichment analysis with disorder context and positional framing, this study aims to clarify the possible functional roles of ORF4 and to explore whether distinct anellovirus lineages encode divergent regulatory strategies.

Methodology

Isolate Selection

The selection of sequences and structural models (PDBs) for this study was designed to compare the functional architecture of the ORF4 protein across the two primary lineages of the *Anelloviridae* family, TTV and TTMDV. Eight representative isolates, (TTV10, TTV6, TTV20, TTV24, TTMDV1, TTMDV7, TTMDV9, and TTMDV10), were selected for analysis.

Table 1: Sequence identifiers, structural confidence metrics, and amino-acid length of analyzed ORF4 proteins from representative anellovirus isolates

Isolate Name	Uniprot ID	Length (aa)	Mean pLDDT Score
Torque Teno Virus 10	Q8V7F6	280	63.5
Torque Teno Virus 6	Q914N2	273	64.6
Torque Teno Virus 20	Q91CZ9	262	67.3
Torque Teno Virus 24	Q91CY8	275	65.4
Torque Teno Midi Virus 1	A4GZ90	261	67.6
Torque Teno Midi Virus 7	A7VLW1	262	68.5
Torque Teno Midi Virus 9	A7VLY1	263	68.0
Torque Teno Midi Virus 10	A7VLY5	256	71.6

Table Caption: Mean predicted Local Distance Difference Test (pLDDT) scores derived from AlphaFold structural models of ORF4 proteins. The pLDDT score represents the average per-residue confidence of the predicted structure, where values below ~70 generally indicate regions of low structural confidence consistent with intrinsically disordered protein segments.¹²

Sequence Retrieval and Dataset Construction

Sequence lengths ranged from 256 to 280 amino acids. Physicochemical properties including molecular weight and theoretical isoelectric point (pI) were calculated using EMBOSS Pepstats. These values were used to characterize basic physicochemical variation among ORF4 proteins prior to motif analysis.

Multiple Sequence Alignment

To evaluate positional conservation and enable comparative mapping of predicted motifs, ORF4 amino acid sequences were aligned using MAFFT v7 with default parameters. Motif positions were subsequently interpreted relative to the aligned sequence coordinates when assessing positional clustering across isolates.

Prediction of Short Linear Motifs

SLIMs were identified using the ELM resource (ELM database v5.5). Each ORF4 sequence was submitted individually for motif prediction with a filter value of 80.

ELM identifies candidate motifs based on experimentally validated consensus patterns corresponding to known eukaryotic protein-protein interaction interfaces, post-translational modification sites, and trafficking signals. For each predicted motif instance, the following information was recorded: motif class identifier, matched sequence region, residue position within the protein, predicted functional class.

Null Model Construction Using Shuffled Sequences

A shuffled-sequence null model was generated to estimate background motif frequency.

Shuffled control sequences were generated from the ungapped ORF4 sequences using a dipeptide-preserving ($k = 2$) shuffle algorithm, which randomizes sequence order while maintaining the original dipeptide composition. Preservation of dipeptide frequencies helps control for compositional bias and local sequence structure that could otherwise inflate motif occurrence rates.

For each original ORF4 sequence, 20 shuffled replicates were generated, producing a background dataset representing the expected motif distribution under random sequence organization while preserving local residue composition.

Motif Enrichment Analysis

Each shuffled sequence was analyzed using the same ELM motif prediction workflow applied to the real ORF4 sequences. Motif counts from the shuffled dataset were used to calculate a background expectation for each motif class.

Motif enrichment was evaluated by comparing motif density in the real ORF4 proteins to the mean motif density observed across the shuffled controls. Enrichment was expressed as:

$$\text{Motif enrichment} = \frac{\text{Motif density}_{\text{Real}}}{\text{Motif density}_{\text{Shuffled}}}$$

Motifs showing densities substantially greater than the shuffled expectation were considered candidates for functional retention, whereas motifs occurring at frequencies comparable to shuffled controls were interpreted as likely background matches resulting from amino acid composition.

Positional Distribution Analysis

To evaluate whether enriched motifs exhibited structured positional organization, motif coordinates were normalized by protein length to produce relative positional values:

$$\text{Relative position} = \frac{\text{Motif start position}}{\text{Protein length}}$$

Relative positions were then compared across isolates to identify clustering patterns (for example N-terminal, central, or C-terminal enrichment). Motifs displaying consistent positional bias across isolates were interpreted as potential architectural elements rather than randomly distributed matches.

Integration with Structural Disorder Predictions

Predicted motif locations were evaluated in the context of intrinsic structural disorder and AlphaFold confidence scores (pLDDT). Because many functional SLiMs occur within disordered or flexible regions, motif instances located in predicted disordered segments or at disorder-order transition boundaries were considered particularly consistent with potential regulatory interaction sites.

Results

Physicochemical Characteristics of ORF4 Proteins

Physicochemical analysis of ORF4 proteins using EMBOSS Pepstats revealed several compositional differences between viral lineages. Although ORF4 proteins are similar in length (256–280 amino acids), they exhibit notable variation in charge distribution and residue composition.

Several TTV ORF4 proteins display strong enrichment in arginine residues, resulting in highly basic isoelectric points ($\text{pI} \approx 10\text{--}10.6$) and elevated net positive charge compared with TTMDV proteins ($\text{pI} \approx 7\text{--}9.7$). In addition, TTV ORF4 sequences contain elevated proline content, with several isolates exceeding 13–15% proline residues. Across all isolates, approximately 50–60% of residues fall into the “small residue” category defined by Pepstats.

These compositional features indicate that ORF4 proteins contain large regions enriched in charged, proline-rich, and small residues.

Table 2: Physicochemical characteristics of ORF4 proteins from candidate TTV and TTMDV isolates.

Isolate	Residues	Molecular Weight (Da)	pI	Net Charge	Polar (%)	Non-polar (%)	Charged (%)	Basic (%)	Acidic (%)
TTMDV10	256	29,200.80	6.96	2.5	51.56	48.44	30.08	16.41	13.67
TTMDV9	263	30,009.71	7.98	5.5	54.75	45.25	31.56	17.49	14.07
TTMDV7	262	29,504.90	9.68	12.0	54.20	45.80	27.86	17.18	10.69
TTMDV1	261	29,491.97	7.99	5.5	55.17	44.83	29.50	16.48	13.03
TTV24	275	29,912.77	10.48	15.0	41.82	58.18	26.18	16.36	9.82
TTV20	262	28,759.25	10.62	14.5	43.89	56.11	26.72	16.79	9.92
TTV6	273	30,205.82	10.10	11.5	45.42	54.58	27.11	16.12	10.99
TTV10	280	30,439.06	10.07	16.5	42.50	57.50	26.07	16.79	9.29

Table Caption: Physicochemical parameters calculated from ORF4 amino acid sequences using the EMBOSS Pepstats program. Reported values include sequence length, predicted molecular weight, theoretical isoelectric point, net charge, and proportions of polar, non-polar, charged, basic, and acidic residues. These values reflect compositional differences among ORF4 proteins across analyzed isolates.

Table 3: Group-level summary of physicochemical properties of ORF4 proteins from candidate TTV and TTMDV isolates.

Group	Mean Length	Mean pI	Mean Charge	Polar (%)	Non-polar (%)
TTMDV	260.5 aa	8.15	6.38	~53.9	~46.1
TTV	272.5 aa	10.32	14.38	~43.4	~56.6

Table Caption: Mean physicochemical properties of ORF4 proteins grouped by viral lineage (TTV and TTMDV). Values represent averages calculated from the individual sequence properties shown in Figure 2, including mean sequence length, theoretical isoelectric point, net charge, and residue composition categories.

*SLiM Identification and Null-Model Comparison***Figure 1:** Distribution of predicted SLiMs in ORF4 proteins of representative TTV and TTMDV isolates.

Figure Legend: Heatmap showing the raw counts of predicted short linear motifs identified in ORF4 proteins using the ELM resource. Rows represent viral isolates and columns represent motif classes. Values correspond to the total number of motif matches detected within each ORF4 sequence, without normalization or enrichment correction. The motifs shown include PP1 phosphatase docking motifs, proline-rich SH3-binding ligands, canonical 14-3-3 interaction motifs, and N-glycosylation motifs. Colour intensity reflects motif abundance, with higher values indicating greater numbers of predicted motif instances. TTV isolates display higher densities of SH3-binding motifs and consistent PP1 docking motifs relative to TTMDV sequences, illustrating lineage-specific differences.

Three motif classes exceeded background expectations in multiple isolates. The most prominent signal corresponded to the PP1 docking motif (DOC_PP1_RVXF_1) within the TTV lineage. Motif density in isolates TTV6, TTV20, and TTV24 exceeded shuffled controls by approximately 7.4–7.7-fold. These motifs exhibited a strong positional bias toward the C-terminal region (median relative position ≈ 0.79).

Proline-rich SH3-binding ligands (LIG_SH3_3) were also enriched in TTV isolates, with motif density approximately 2.1–2.7-fold above the shuffled background. These motifs formed clusters within the N-terminal and central portions of the protein (median relative positions approximately 0.24–0.70).

A third motif class, canonical 14-3-3 binding motifs (LIG_14-3-3_CanoR_1), showed enrichment in a subset of sequences. The strongest signal was observed in TTV6 (~ 4.9 -fold enrichment) and TTMDV10 (~ 2.6 -fold enrichment).

Several additional motif classes, including Pin1 docking motifs and consensus phosphorylation motifs associated with kinases such as GSK3 and CK1, did not exceed the shuffled background.

Comparative analysis also revealed lineage-specific differences in motif composition. TTV ORF4 proteins displayed greater enrichment of PP1 docking motifs and SH3-binding ligands, whereas TTMDV sequences showed comparatively lower densities of these motifs and instead exhibited modest enrichment for alternative motif classes, including N-glycosylation motifs.

Discussion

The compositional and motif analyses presented here suggest that ORF4 proteins possess characteristics typical of intrinsically disordered viral regulatory proteins.

The high arginine content observed in several TTV ORF4 proteins results in strongly basic isoelectric points and increased positive charge, features commonly associated with transient regulatory interfaces and electrostatic interactions with negatively charged cellular components. This compositional bias is consistent with the enrichment of PP1 docking motifs identified in the SLiM analysis, which are often located within flexible regions that recruit host phosphatase complexes.¹³

Similarly, the elevated proline content observed in TTV ORF4 proteins is compatible with the clustering of SH3-binding motifs detected within these sequences.¹⁴ Proline-rich regions disrupt regular secondary structure formation and frequently serve as interaction platforms for SH3-domain-containing proteins¹⁵, suggesting that ORF4 may participate in host signaling networks through modular protein-protein interaction interfaces.

The high proportion of small residues across ORF4 sequences further supports this interpretation. Such residue compositions are characteristic of intrinsically disordered regions, which lack stable tertiary structure but can adopt multiple conformations that facilitate interactions with diverse host proteins.¹⁶

Together, these features support a model in which ORF4 functions as an intrinsically disordered regulatory adaptor rather than a catalytic protein. In this framework, the protein likely operates by recruiting host signaling factors through short linear motifs embedded within flexible regions.

The motif architecture also differs between viral lineages. TTV ORF4 proteins display enrichment and positional clustering of PP1 docking motifs and SH3-binding ligands, whereas TTMDV sequences show reduced densities of these motifs and suggestive enrichment for alternative motif classes. These differences imply that TTV and TTMDV viruses may employ distinct strategies for interacting with host regulatory pathways despite maintaining broadly similar protein lengths and genomic organization.

Overall, the combination of compositional features and motif organization supports the hypothesis that ORF4 proteins act as flexible host-interaction scaffolds that contribute to viral regulation through motif-mediated recruitment of cellular factors.

Conclusion

Comparative analysis of ORF4 proteins from representative TTV and TTMDV isolates identified recurrent short linear motifs embedded within largely intrinsically disordered regions. Motif density comparisons against composition-preserving shuffled controls indicated that several interaction motifs, most notably PP1 docking sites and proline-rich SH3-binding ligands, occur at elevated densities in TTV isolates and display non-random positional organization along the protein sequence. In particular, PP1 docking motifs cluster toward the C-terminus, while SH3-binding motifs are concentrated within N-terminal and central regions. These patterns support a model in which ORF4 functions as a flexible interaction scaffold capable of recruiting host regulatory proteins. Differences in motif composition between TTV and TTMDV isolates further suggest lineage-specific remodeling of host interaction interfaces within *Anelloviridae*.

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